

Lars Von Trier Cinema: Europe and America Trilogy

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Abstract

Feminist thought and women's movements also criticize the world that cinema has shown. In the cinema, women are accepted and criticized as a product of the male gaze. The woman, the innocent young girl and the mother with their roles in the family, is thought of as someone who should look beautiful, in love with harmony in social life. The female representations formed by the male point of view see the woman as passive. In this point of view, when women become a factor, they oppose their social roles. From the beginning of the 20th century, when cinema became a sector, to the present, women are represented with certain typologies. In this research, female representation in cinema and feminist theory are discussed, and Lars Von Trier's European and American Trilogy is analyzed with semiotic method and various data are tried to be revealed.

Keywords: *Lars Von Trier, European Cinema, American Cinema, Feminism, Cinema*

1. Introduction

Cinema; while it retains the ability to show reality, the issue of reality has not been on the agenda since the emergence of cinema. With the style of expression in the cinema, reality is considered as technical and aesthetic. The subject of motion pictures is the interpretation of life in a creative way, even though it is similar to real life. The interpretation of the cinema against the reality shows the artistic quality of the cinema. Films present various ideas about life to the audience through aesthetics. When talking about cinema, first of all, it is necessary to talk about 'reality' outside the context of cinema. The Merriam-Webster dictionary (2015) defines 'truth' as "truth or the property of being compatible with reality". Like reality, reality is abstract concepts that are difficult to define. When viewed in the context of the representation of reality in cinema, it is possible to conclude that what cinema can do is to produce meaning and that it can draw this in relation to other meanings, not abstract or criterion truth measures (Wollen, 2009:426). According to Wollen, this is about reality, but when we talk about cinematic devices, we start talking about 'reality'. The seemingly natural environment and the use of costumes imply a logical way of telling the story. This seemingly "realistic" depiction of the world is not the real world itself. Supporting this view of Wollen, Susan Sontag has the following to say

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about reality: *In the age of cameras, new demands are coming for reality. The real may not be scary enough and therefore needs to be developed; or it should be revived convincingly (2004:57).*

In the 20th century in Western societies, various groups and identities seek their rights. Blacks, women, homosexuals, and other ethnicities seek their rights in society. Throughout history, the lack of visibility of these groups in society and the denial of their rights are the starting points of their struggles. Feminist thought and women's movements are among them. The women's movements, which became active with the end of the 19th century, continued in the 20th century in various forms. Despite some differences, the common idea of women's movements can be expressed as rethinking the role of women in society.

It is thought that women have been seen in a socially separate place throughout history. Socially, women are not free like men, and the social roles assigned to them are limited. Presenting the role of women from home to business life as a birthright for them is the starting point of the criticism of women's movements. This criticism shows itself in every part of society such as education, law, sexuality, economy and art. The representation of women in works of art is criticized by women's movements. While art tells about women, it takes these situations into consideration and women are represented with certain patterns in visual art.

Although the works are seen as valuable in terms of aesthetic quality, they can bring a view to the fore with their way of representation, and artists can do this consciously or unconsciously. Women's movements, on the other hand, state that this approach is against women while evaluating art and art history. They claim that women are not shown in works of art other than in accepted roles. The woman is seen in 19th century western painting with three types of women that can be defined as "art fairy, seducer, madonna". It can be stated that all three types of women gain definition with their moral and religious, love and emotional relationships.

It can be suggested that there are certain patterns of female characterizations in the cinema. The 'mother' who protects the family and is compatible with the society, the 'fairy' that distracts and inspires those who admire her and the man she loves, and the 'seductive woman' characterizations that are contrary to social roles and reject all these can be expressed as a summary of women's typologies in the history of cinema. Feminist thought and women's movements also criticize the world that cinema has shown. In the cinema, women are accepted and criticized as a product of the male gaze. The woman, the innocent young girl and the mother with their roles in the family, is thought of as someone who should look beautiful, in love with harmony in social life. The female representations formed by the male point of view see the woman as passive. In this point of view, when women are active, they oppose their social roles.

It is claimed that the changing perception and thought of femininity and the representations of women in the cinema also differ. From the beginning of the 20th century, when cinema became a sector, to the present, women are represented with certain typologies. On the other hand, in

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the 1980s, when women's movements increased, it is seen that the representations of women in the cinema changed. Over time, the woman turns into a figure who knows that she has rights in society and tries to fight for these rights. The woman who moves to the center of the events takes the place of the woman who is waiting for her hero in the cinema.

It can be said that the cinema of the famous director Lars von Trier was influenced by the changes in world cinema. Trier did not attach much importance to female characters in the early years of his career. It can be said that after Carl Dreyer shot the movie "Medea", which he could not shoot, female characters gained importance in his films. This claim is also supported by the director's cinematography. Female characters are at the center of the films in the films 'Europa, Breaking the Waves, Idiots, Dance in the Dark, Dogville, Manderlay, Antichrist, Nymphomaniac Vol I and II', which Trier shot after the movie "Medea".

In this research, female representation in cinema and feminist theory are discussed, and Lars Von Trier's European and American Trilogy is analyzed with semiotic method and various data are tried to be revealed. In the first part of the research, there are various information about Representation of Women in Cinema, Representation and Feminism. In the second part, information about semiotic analysis is given. In the third chapter, the summary and semiotic analysis of the films are made and the study is concluded.

2. Representation of Women in Cinema, Representation and Feminism

2.1. Representation

The usage area of the word representation is quite wide. In TDK, representation is defined as: "acting on behalf of someone or a community", "for example" (TDK, 2019). The Latin usage of the word 'representation' means "to reveal, to make into existence" in ancient Greek culture. This meaning, which was first used in inanimate objects, is then defined as an activity of "depicting, presenting, performing a play or painting". This definition, which was frequently used in western culture in the 15th century, was used in the 17th century to "point to an entity that was replaced". With the transfer of Stuart Hall, the word 'representation' in English means the following (Pitkin, 2014:233)

1. To represent, describe, describe, or describe, picture, or visualize anything; is to put an image of it in the senses or in our minds.
2. To represent also means to hold one's place, to set an example, to mean, to symbolize.

Therefore, representation is a phenomenon related to how language and reality in the outside world are related. At this point, Hall states that "the real environment in which ideologies are effective is consciousness and language practice" because meanings are created through language. Gregory Currie's general approach to representation; "Representations expand our

epistemic access to things in the world. If they are reliable, they can give us their information even if we do not have access to those things” (Currie, 1995:49).

2.2. Women's Representation in Feminist Theory

The word 'feminism' began to be used in western culture at the end of the nineteenth century (Humm, 2002:17). Feminism states that women do not want to be limited only to domestic roles in the power of men, and that women are free-willed beings. However, this basic meaning of the word has varied throughout history in terms of attitude and method. Feminism does not have a single definition, as it is not a single type of theory. Feminism is in relation to other theories. Some of these theories are; Structuralism, Existentialism, Marxism and Psychoanalysis are the theories (Donovan, 2010).

The word feminism became widespread in the 1960s and 1970s (Pekerman, 2012:37). The 70s are seen as the time when the feminist movement continued political action and adopted critical methods. Feminism's goal of strengthening institutionally becomes clear in this period. For this reason, political critical attitudes and theoretical research come together. Especially in this period, "with the influence of the Women's Movement, women, the history of cinema and films are started to be viewed with different eyes" (Smelik, 2008:2).

It is advocated that women leave their social roles in this period, and the problems experienced by women who are married and have children while undertaking these duties gain importance (Taş, 2016:170). Beauvoir's statement that “women's liberation will start from their bellies” states that women carry a new generation within themselves by adopting their biological identities (Sevim, 2005:51). Feminism tries to bring new perspectives to women's perspective in the face of defining the body with the roles that society has presented to women in terms of the representation of women's identity. The 3rd wave feminism movement, which started in the 90s, criticizes the previous feminist wave from various aspects. The first criticism is that feminism is considered in terms of middle and upper class women. The idea of femininity is universally accepted in this wave. As well as the problems of middle-class and white western women, the problems of women in black or other ethnic groups are beginning to be addressed (Taş, 2016).

Third wave feminists are more concerned with micro-policies such as women's empowerment, sexuality and violence against women. In addition, in terms of content, they touch on very different subjects compared to the other wave. Third-wave feminism is particularly concerned with issues that oppress and limit women, and they see and support broad education (Humm, 2002: 37). In the history of feminism, women's identity in general has a social aspect. Congenital female identity is accepted biologically, and female identity in terms of social roles has been taught and imposed on women throughout history. Feminism argues that its methods are multi-layered. Political and social institutions such as university, school, family, roles such

as woman to fall in love with, good wife, motherhood, values such as purity, youth and beauty are presented to women with social acceptance. It can be said that one of these ways is cinema (Smelik, 2008:4).

2.3.Feminist Theory in Cinema

In the art of cinema; from the very beginning of cinema, it is discussed in terms of reality. Early theorists such as Bela Balazs, Sergei Eisenstein, Rudolf Arnheim, and Hugo Munsterberg interpret reality in cinema with the formal language of cinema (Andrew, 2007). The problem of how the cinema device interprets reality is mostly understood with technical problems such as exterior shooting, interior shooting, light, editing and montage.

When it comes to representations of classes, ethnic identities and genders in cinema, formalist approaches are insufficient. Methods such as queer theory, psychoanalysis, feminism, semiotics and Marxism are used to examine these issues. These theories criticize the representation of identities in the cinema, and while doing this, evaluate them on the axis of truth-false. "Women become feminists by recognizing and criticizing the power of symbolic misrepresentation of women" (Humm, 2002:19). For these approaches, culture imposes direct or indirect pressures on the person. "Women carry the "images of women" formed by the dominant culture within themselves, and while they are on the path of change, they have to struggle not only with external pressures and obstacles, but also with these definitions of the dominant culture they carry within themselves" (Berkday, 2012:18).

In the feminist cinema theory, the aesthetic and political research of the representation of women in the cinema is carried out. With the proposal of women's cinema, they present films produced by women, films that appeal to women, and films related to women. The main interest of the feminist cinema theory is "women are not represented as women in the mass media and whether this is a situation that has always been and should be in cinematic presentation". This target also includes the targets of feminist literary criticism (Özden, 2014: 194).

While feminist cinema theory and criticism benefited from Marxism in its early days, it later made use of psychoanalysis and semiotics (Özden, 2014:192). Laura Mulvey thinks that latent meanings can be reached in cinema with the help of semiotics. It was the work of Claire Johnson who was the first to systematically study semiotics. They see artistic form as a means of expression with semiotics. The images of women presented on the screen are a product of patriarchal ideologies. She is not a real and natural woman. The woman is the one that exists in the cinema narrative, it is not real, it is created in the story (Özden, 2014:195).

The representation of women is seen in the cinema as an image that is enjoyable to watch for the audience, and this situation continues throughout the history of cinema. It can be said that this situation continues today. On the other hand, it can be said that there are many examples that want to go beyond the representation of women in this way. The number of women working

behind the screen is increasing with the entry of women who receive cinema education into the cinema industry. The widespread use of the "positive discrimination" phenomenon in the women's movement since the 1980s has led to the questioning of women's identity in culture and media and to bring about changes (Timisi, 2011:61).

2.4. Women's Representations in Cinema History

The first serious critical approaches to the representation of women in cinema emerged in the 1960s. The libertarian movement that emerged in 1968 also lays the groundwork for events and departures that can be considered radical in many areas. Women's movements are also beginning to express themselves with more radical thoughts and are making harsh intellectual attacks on power. In the early periods of feminism, cinema was seen as one of the communication tools that could be transformed into the struggle area of women's movements. In this context, the first serious intellectual debates about feminist film theory develop after that. In particular, with the theoretical output grounded by Marxist thinkers, discussions arise that cinema is not just about what is shown, but that its signs are imposed through filmic texts (Derman, 1994:2). The attitudes of feminist movements towards cinema differ, based on the fact of a cinema practice in which very few women are included in the main creation process, working as various intermediate elements in the film industry over the years. According to them;

Films can be used as an ideological device to counter the stereotypical images of women presented by the male-dominated media, and to make women aware of their secondary position in the male-dominated society, where they often play subordinate roles. The ideological character of the political struggle and purpose in feminist filmmaking also provides the development of a feminist cinema theory. Feminist cinema theory in the early period adopts sexuality and its presentation as the main focus of interest in relations with the dominance of male power in a male-dominated society (Smelik 2008:6).

It is seen that the feminist theory did not progress in a clear line until the 1980s and could change according to different solution productions and perspectives. The fact that the solutions, especially about the rejection of the father's language, do not fit well with practice, shifts the theory's main starting point to change the dictated mentality from its main focus (Nelmes 1998:75).

Feminist film theory decides to use the language of the father, based on the thesis that the radical breakaway method that it proposed in its beginnings would not be practical either, and blocked the escape routes from the masculine system in the field of cultural representation. As a result, the proposed efforts to make the woman subject to a new mental reading by not detaching them

from their historical context are possible with the rational use of cultural representation tools. All these require creating a new way of seeing and reading and teaching it to a new generation.

3. Methodology

Semiotics is expressed as the science of signs; It is examined as a sign system of any vehicle. Semiotics examines all the elements that can be used in the name of communication. Natural languages, fashion, literary works, money, advertising posters, a theatrical performance, a musical work, any architectural arrangement, the structure of transportation routes in a country, the layout of a city, traffic signs, images, used by people for communication purposes. The alphabet, in short, is a string of different sign units, either communicative or non-communicative. These system units are generally called indicators (Rifat, 2009). The name of semiotics is given by the English philosopher John Locke (1632-1704). Locke argues that semiotics, which he first expressed as the 'doctrine of signs' by using the expression 'semeiotike', should be one of the three basic branches of science. After Locke, many thinkers and writers deal with the examination of non-linguistic and linguistic signs in their works, and they follow Locke in this context.

The foundation date of modern semiotics dates back to the beginning of the 20th century. Philosopher Charles Sanders Peirce and linguist Ferdinand de Saussure were laying the foundations of modern semiotics almost at the same time, unaware of each other (Rifat, 2009). C. Peirce, a logician and also the founder of pragmatism, designs a general theory of signs using the concept of semeiotic. Peirce, who defended an understanding of semiotics on the basis of logic, focuses on the logical function of signs. While Peirce, who made semiotics an independent discipline, systematized his ideas with this method, the linguist Ferdinand da Saussure describes the science he designed as "sémiologie" as "a branch of science whose place is predetermined and will be established in the future." Unlike Peirce, Saussure creates a dual structure as "signifiant" (see you) and "signifie" (shown) (Rifat, 2009).

Roland Barthes, another important name of contemporary semiotics, mostly works on popular culture analysis with his unique approach. The analysis method developed by Barthes does not aim to communicate, but includes some meaningful facts (furniture, clothing, etc.). Barthes connects all these to semiotics through the phenomenon of signification, and focuses on the relations between signs and secondary signifieds or connotations (Vardar, 2001). Barthes, one of the representatives of the Saussure tradition, argues that, unlike Saussure, linguistics should not be a part of semiotics, but semiotics as a part of linguistics (Erkman, 1987).

4. Representation in the Cinema of Lars Von Trier

4.1. The Life of the Director

Lars Von Trier was born in 1956. In 1969, he played in the children's TV series "Secret Summer" in Denmark. He shot the films "Nocturn" in 1980 and "The Last Detail" in 1981. The director's first success was the award he received with the movie "Nocturn" at a festival held in Munich (Tapper, 2015: 87). After a series of short films, the director shoots the movie "Crime Element" in 1984, "Outbreak" in 1987 and "Medea" in 1988. Completing the "Europe Trilogy" with the 1991 film "Europe", the director makes a sound with the 1996 film "Crossing the Waves". In the ongoing process, Trier is shooting the 1998 film "Idiots", which belongs to the Dogma movement he is in. He won awards in Cannes with the movie "Dancing in the Dark" in 2000. The documentary film "Five Barriers" in 2003, "Dogville" in 2003 and "Manderlay" in 2005 are followed by and popularized the name Trier with these films. These two films from the "America" trilogy, the third of which have not been shot yet, are followed by the 2011 film "Melancholy". This movie is followed by "Nymphomaniacs Vol. 1 and 2" dated 2012. Trier's latest film is 2018's "The House Jack Built".

He has been a controversial director throughout Trier's career. Critics and audiences offer various opinions about his cinema. Trier's artistic vision is to make films that the audience would not want to be told. Trier's aim is to make "counter-films" (Schwander, 2015: 15). Expressing his desire to make disturbing films from the beginning of his career, Trier becomes persona non grata with his statements at the Cannes Film Festival. The subjects in some of his films are the reasons why Trier is disturbing. Richard Huston describes Trier's cinema as "cinema against ethics", with the thought that it sets aside accepted rules (Larsen, 2015: 53). Trier's aesthetic idea is to "glorify the ugliness and show that beauty can be found everywhere" (as cited in Güntay, 2018: 95). Ugliness, an unusual narrative may require them to try an unusual style in examining the subject (Michelsen, 2015: 10).

Trier has been frequently criticized by film critics in Denmark since the first years of his career, and every film he shot is seen as scandalous. However, almost every film he made is nominated for festivals such as Cannes. He makes films that make him famous in the international arena, he is criticized in European cinema, and he draws attention in American cinema with the mid-1990s. His attitude towards sexuality and nudity is cited as the reason why Trier's directorship is characterized as scandalous. It is stated that these features, which are evident in Trier's cinemas, are related to the cinema tradition Trier has come from. It can be seen that there is a tradition of sexuality and nudity in Scandinavian cinema, including Danish cinema (Stevenson, 2005: 154). Film historians state that Trier, who was influenced by Dreyer, was an important filmmaker who came after Dreyer in Danish cinema (Robinson, 2015:11).

4.2.Semiotic Analysis of Films

4.2.1. Europe Trilogy

4.2.1.1. The Element of Crime (1984)

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Movie Tag:

Director: Lars von Trier.

Screenplay: Stephen Wakelam, William Quarshie, Niels Vørsel and Lars von Trier.

Cast: Esmond Knight, Michael Elphick, Ahmed El Shenawi, Jerold Wells, Me Me Lai

The main character of the movie, detective Fisher, aims to solve the serial killer murders in Europe. The detective is also a former cop. After years of living in the Middle East, he returned to Europe. In the city he came from, dark events take place and a serial murder is committed. Fisher is helped by a friend who has a book called 'The Element of Crime'. Fisher tries to solve the murders with the help of this book. Fisher's methods are contrary to his profession. The Element of Crime is among the early masterpieces of director Lers Von Trier. After this film, the director creates the Dogma movement. The film hovers between the themes of film noir and science fiction.

Figure 1: The fight of a large group

Indicator	Indicative	Shown
Crowd and fight	A person beaten by a group	Violence

Figure 2: Doctor informing the detective as a result of autopsy

Indicator	Indicative	Shown
Corpse	Doctor and Detective	Detections made as a result of autopsy

4.2.1.2. Epidemic (1987)

Director: Lars von Trier

Screenplay: Niels Vørsel and Lars von Trier

Cast: Udo Kier, Svend Ali Hamann, Colin Gilder, Michael Gelting, Ole Ernst, Allan De Waal

The film opens with the scene of two filmmakers trying to prepare the script for the movie "Police and Prostitute". The computer where people with limited time save their scenarios breaks down. Since the scenario is gone with the broken computer, these two start to write a new scenario. This newly written scenario is the scenario of "The Epidemic". While the audience is watching the writing of this script, they also start watching the scenes of the movie "Palagin". Throughout the movie, the effects and dimensions of the epidemic are shown.

It is the subject of the film that an idealist doctor goes from the center to the countryside in order to prevent the epidemic in Europe. In the movie, the epidemic in the scenario prepared by the duo begins to occur in real life as well. The main character in the script is Dr. Mesmer goes to the place where the epidemic is for discovery. Screenwriters are also doing research on the

epidemic. The two worlds in the movie mix after a certain period of time, and the epidemic takes over real life. Screenwriters and their friends also get sick.

Figure 3: Dr. Mesmer's descent from the helicopter

Indicator	Indicative	Shown
Get off the helicopter	Person getting out of helicopter	Dr. Mesmer's miraculous descent from the helicopter

Figure 4: The woman caught in the epidemic

Indicator	Indicative	Shown
A woman	The woman caught in the epidemic	Suffering due to the epidemic

4.2.1.3. Europa (1991).

Director: Lars von Trier

Screenplay: Niels Vørsel and Lars von Trier

Cast: Benny Poulsen, Max von Sydow, Eddie Constantine, Henning Jensen, Jørgen Reenberg, Erik Mørk, Ernst-Hugo Järegård, Ernst-Hugo Järegård, Barbara Sukowa, Jean-Marc Barr.

Leo Kessler, who came to his uncle in Germany in 1945 to work at the train station, is an American-European character. At that time, a group of Nazi supporters known as werewolves assassinate leaders traveling by train. Kessler grows emotionally close to his boss's daughter, Katharina Hartmann, and a romance develops between the two. Kessler is happy and considering marriage to Katharina. But werewolves kidnap Katharina. The werewolves ask Leo to plant a bomb at an address. Leo accepts this condition in order to dry Katharina and plant the bomb, but defuses the bomb at the last moment. Learning that Katharina is one of the werewolves, Leo takes the trainees hostage. Kessler drives the train towards the bridge where the bomb is placed, detonates the bomb and destroys the bridge. The train sinks into the river, and Kessler and many others die.

Figure 5: Leo Kessler riding a train with a gun

Indicator	Indicative	Shown
Gun	The person walking with the gun and the people following him	Fear and uneasiness experienced by those who see the gunman

Figure 6: Invitation to dinner

Indicator	Indicative	Shown
Message	Letter	Invitation to dinner

4.2.2. American Trilogy(2003-2005)

4.2.2.1.Dogville (2003)

Director: Lars von Trier

Screenplay: Lars von Trier

Cast: Nicole Kidman, Harriet Andersson, Lauren Bacall, Blair Brown, Patricia Clarkson, Ben Gazzara, Siobhan Fallon.

Escaping from the mafia, Grace's path ends up in a town called Dogville. In town, the young poet Tom finds Grace. Introducing Grace to the townsfolk, Tom falls in love with Grace. Tom tries to persuade the townspeople, who regard him as a stranger, to accept Grace. After a certain period of time, Grace makes herself accepted and is loved by the townspeople. However, after the police arrive in town to search for Grace, the townspeople begin to think they are doing something wrong. Grace begins to be seen as a wanted fugitive and the townspeople begin to mistreat her. After these behaviors, Grace tries to escape from the town but fails. Grace falls into the captivity of the townspeople. At the end of the movie, Grace's father, who came to town with his men, learns what happened to Grace and has the townspeople killed.

Figure 7: The townspeople meet Grace.

Indicator	Indicative	Shown
People	Grace ve townspeople	Indecision and anxiety

Figure 8: The townspeople learn of the search warrant for Grace

Indicator	Indicative	Shown
Notice	Townspeople reading the police search notice	Rush and fear

4.2.2.2. Menderlay (2005)

Director: Lars von Trier

Screenplay: Lars von Trier

Cast: Bryce Dallas Howard, Isaach De Bankolé, Danny Glover, Willem Dafoe, Michaël Abiteboul, Lauren Bacall, Jean-Marc Barr, Geoffrey Bateman, Virgile Bramly, Ruben Brinkman, Doña Croll, Jeremy Davies, Lle Holdera Gideon, Mona Hammond, Ginny .

In this sequel to the movie Dogville, Grace goes to a town where slavery is still practiced despite being banned. Grace, who has taken over the town of Manderlay, tries to free the slaves. Its aim is to establish a democratic and equal order as in 'Dogville'. Although Grace makes an effort to

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make the slaves feel that they are the owners of their work, after a certain period of time, she realizes that something has not changed. Realizing that the slaves in the town are willing to accept the existing order of slavery and cannot accept the order she is trying to bring, Grace sees that the democracy she aims for has not materialized and finally leaves the town.

Figure 9: Mother abusing her son in Menderlay

Indicator	Indicative	Shown
People	Mother abusing her son	Violence

Görsel 10: Dialogue of slaves with Grace

Indicator	Indicative	Shown
People	Talking Grace and slaves	The bad psychology of slaves

Conclusion and Evaluation

The study concluded that there is a point of view in the relationship between cinema and representation about the construction of the meaning specific to the nature of representation, social and historical acceptances, and the meanings of representations in the background. The fact that the feminist theory says that the point of view towards women is masculine means that the same point of view can be considered in cinema. In terms of cinema, sectoral and aesthetic, female characters have caused the social female identity to be brought to the cinema screen. She appeared on the screen in categories such as woman, good mother, innocent young girl, beautiful young girl. However, these representations constantly take on new appearances over time due to the social position of women and the changes brought about by women's movements in the society on women's rights. Therefore, the representation of women in the art of cinema in the twentieth century, which is discussed within the scope of the study, has to be seen as related to the changes in periodic perceptions.

In the context of this study, which was carried out in the axis of the theoretical framework for the purpose of the research, semiotic analysis was made. In the films examined within the scope of the study, female characters were seen as opposed to their social roles. It can be said that women in Trier's cinema are in an effort to be in action, just like in the 80's in the history of cinema, women are free and aim to be in action. In Trier, women have characteristics such as changing things, pursuing important goals, being superior to male characters. While evaluating Trier's female characters, it can be said that they can gain meaning around the concept of crime.

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